

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

Is This the Right Fit? Evaluating Funding Opportunities for Your Research

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP
Consultants Program

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About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution.

The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

Executive Summary

“You should just apply for every grant that’s relevant to your interests.” Well-intentioned chairs, directors, deans, and mentors have been telling first-time or early-career investigators that for decades. It might have been true in the past, but it is certainly not true now. Worse, it’s actually harmful advice. The goal of the investigator (and the research support professionals who work with them) should be to identify the sponsor or program that best fits the work they want to do right now, at their current institution, and given their background, training, and education - with a secondary goal of developing, over time, a relationship with one or more sponsors that can potentially support their work for the duration of their career or their current research arc, whichever is longer. This resource will help both investigators and the research support professionals they work with to do those things.

Target Audience

Investigators seeking external funding for their research, scholarship, and creative artistry, and the research development and research administration professionals who assist them.

Authors’ Note: As we don’t know precisely who will be reading our resource, we are making absolutely no assumptions about our audience. Some of our readers may be encountering this information for the first time; others may already be familiar with much of it. We hope that everyone who reads it will find something useful in it.

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RD SAYS:

Look for these author notes throughout. They provide research development insights and best practices to help you submit a successful proposal/application.

Background

Ever done a search for funding opportunities and gotten back a list this long?

The screenshot shows a search results page for funding opportunities. The search criteria are: (keyword (Europe OR Digital Humanities OR Folk or Ethnic Studies OR General Humanities Topics OR History OR Language or Literature) OR keyword_parent (Europe OR Digital Humanities OR Folk or Ethnic Studies OR General... more »). The results are sorted by Relevance and show 4,009 results. The list includes various grants such as Community Project Grants, Washington Stories Fund grants, Don Yoder Prize, Chicago Folklore Prize, Events funding grants, Benjamin A. Botkin Prize, and NEH Long-Term Fellowships. A sidebar on the left provides filters for Recently added, Submission type, Deadline Certainty, Funding types, and Funder types.

Recently added	Count
Last 30 days	1007
Last 14 days	865
Last 7 days	744

Submission type	Count
Limited Submission	108
Other internal coordination required	17

Deadline Certainty	Count
Anticipated	2467
Confirmed	1420

Funding types	Count
Research, Project Grants & Innovation	1410
Fellowships or Post-doctoral Awards	912
Prizes and Awards	903
Travel	583
Scholarships, Training or Burearies	552
more...	

Funder types	Count
Private Foundation or Non-Profit	1470
Professional Society or Association	1219
Academic Institution	831
Non-US National Government	383
State, Province or Local Government	150
more...	

Search Results	Sort by	Deadline	Amount
<input type="checkbox"/> 4,009 Results	Relevance		
<input type="checkbox"/> LIMITED Community Project Grants Florida Humanities Council (FHC)		04 Dec 2024 Application Confirmed	\$10,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Washington Stories Fund grants Humanities Washington (IHW)		Date Unknown	\$5,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Don Yoder Prize American Folklore Society (AFS)		01 Jun 2025 Submission/Entry Anticipated	\$500 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Chicago Folklore Prize American Folklore Society (AFS)		15 Apr 2025 Submission/Entry Anticipated	see record
<input type="checkbox"/> Events funding grants British Association for Victorian Studies (BAVS)		30 Nov 2024 Application Confirmed	£1,000 GBP
<input type="checkbox"/> Benjamin A. Botkin Prize American Folklore Society (AFS)		15 Sep 2025 Nomination Anticipated	\$1,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> NEH Long-Term Fellowships New York Public Library (NYPL)		27 Jan 2025 Application Confirmed	\$45,000 USD

Even if you're super-careful with your search terms, you're often going to be left with at least several hundred potentially worthwhile hits:

RD SAYS:

To get a better understanding of how to structure your funding search to get the best possible signal-to-noise ratio in your results, see the "[Finding Funding: Strategies and Tools for Your Search](#)" resource in the EMERGE library.

The screenshot displays a search results page for funding opportunities. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Home, Funding, Profiles, Conferences, and Awarded Grants. A search bar is on the right with a magnifying glass icon and a 'HELP' button. Below the navigation, the search results are displayed. The search criteria are: (keyword (Europe OR Digital Humanities OR Folk or Ethnic Studies OR General Humanities Topics OR History OR Language or Literature) OR keyword_parent (Europe OR Digital Humanities OR Folk or Ethnic Studies OR General ... more »). There are links for 'Advanced Search', 'Save Search', 'Refine Search', and 'Share Search'. The results are sorted by 'Relevance' and show 568 results. A 'Calendar View' button is in the top right of the results area. The results are listed in a table with columns for 'Deadline' and 'Amount'. The table includes entries for 'Community Project Grants', 'Illinois Humanities Vision Grants', 'Digital Humanities Advancement Grants (DHAG)', 'Multiplier Grants', 'Action Grants', 'Neil Ker memorial fund', and 'Action Grants'. A sidebar on the left contains filters for 'Recently added', 'Submission type', 'Deadline Certainty', 'Funding types', and 'Funder types'.

	Deadline	Amount
<input type="checkbox"/> Community Project Grants Florida Humanities Council (FHC)	04 Dec 2024 Application Confirmed	\$10,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Illinois Humanities Vision Grants Illinois Humanities Council	16 Jan 2025 Application Anticipated	\$2,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Digital Humanities Advancement Grants (DHAG) Office of Digital Humanities (ODH) National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH)	09 Jan 2025 Application Anticipated	\$450,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Multiplier Grants Illinois Humanities Council	15 May 2025 Application Anticipated	\$10,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Action Grants Illinois Humanities Council	16 Jan 2025 Application Anticipated	\$4,000 USD
<input type="checkbox"/> Neil Ker memorial fund The British Academy (DA)	08 Jan 2025 Application Confirmed	£2,000 GBP
<input type="checkbox"/> Action Grants New Jersey Council for the Humanities (NJCH)	31 Mar 2025 Letter of Intent Anticipated	\$15,000 USD

Most investigators (and research support professionals) don't have time to read through a list that long, much less prepare proposals for each of the opportunities on the list. Nor should they!

To paraphrase Dave Stone, "it's not the best ideas that get funded: it's the best-positioned ideas." (Stone, 2009) Part of the positioning work that investigators need to do (and that research development professionals should help them understand how to do it) is to pitch the right idea to the right sponsor (or the right program at a particular sponsor). This resource guide will offer strategies, tips, and best practices for determining the best possible fit between the idea for the project and the funder to approach about supporting it.

RD SAYS:

Remember, some funders have guidelines that cover a specific program - but there may also be general guidelines that apply to all proposals submitted to that funder. For example, both the National Science Foundation (NSF) and the Federal Emergency Management Administration (FEMA) use a "PAPPG." However, NSF's is the Proposal & Award Policies and Procedures Guide, and FEMA's is the Public Assistance Program and Policy Guide - two very different documents, for very different purposes, both called "PAPPG." Be sure to check both sets of guidelines!

Steps for Determining Fit

There are many factors to consider when determining whether or not a given opportunity or funder is right for you and for your project. These are the ones we've found most useful over time, and we present them in a rough order of complexity, from the simplest to the most involved:

1. Is the competition still open?
2. Is everyone on the project team, and all of their institutions, eligible to apply to or receive funding from this funder or program?
3. Does the project match at least one of the priorities the funder or program is interested in supporting?
4. Will your proposal be competitive?
5. Does the program offer enough funding to support the full cost of the project?
6. Does the funder have any restrictions (types of funding available or how funds can be used, topics or questions not supported, on publications or use of intellectual property resulting from the project) that either mean you can't complete the project or that you or your institution are not comfortable accepting?
7. Is the funding mechanism appropriate for you and your institution?
8. Is there enough time before the submission deadline for you and your team to draft a competitive proposal and give all the participating institutions time to review, approve, and submit your proposal?
9. Does everyone on the team (and their respective institutions) have a history with the funder or funder's program - and what is that history?
10. Vibe check - does anything feel off when you consider the funder, its programs, priorities, etc.

There are many terms commonly used to describe funding opportunities. Generally, "solicitation," "request for proposals (RFP)," "request for applications (RFA)," "call for proposals (CFP)," "program announcement (PA)," "notice of funding opportunity (NOFO)," "broad agency announcement (BAA)," "notices of special interest (NOSIs)," and "funding opportunity announcement (FOA)" all refer to the written guidance or instructions for applying to a funding opportunity. Though they can imply nuances about the type of agreement, contract, or funding mechanism, for the purpose of this article, we will use the term "solicitation" as a generic term to cover all the varieties of funding opportunity announcements.

1. Is the competition open?

The first and simplest step is to check whether or not the competition is still open. Competitions close for a number of reasons: some are expressly intended to be one-off or one-and-done and are not repeated. Others (many U.S. Department of Education programs, for instance) are completed cyclically - every two years, every five years, etc. If the competition cycle isn't mentioned in the solicitation or on the funder's website, ask your research development or research administration professional to help you determine if the competition is still open.

2. Is everybody eligible?

Next, verify that you, your institution, and all of your partners and their institutions, are eligible for funding through the opportunity. Some opportunities restrict eligibility for the principal investigator (PI) or the PI's institution only - but others require all members of the team and/or their institutions to meet the eligibility criteria. Be sure to connect with your research development or research administration professionals for guidance on the criteria in the announcement.

Some funders (and funders' programs) restrict eligibility for funding based on location - either of the recipient institution(s) or of where the project work will be conducted. It's always worth checking the solicitation to be sure it's suitable for the project and the project team. It may help to divide eligibility into different categories: (1) institutional eligibility; (2) applicant eligibility; and (3) project scope eligibility.

Make sure to read the **entire** solicitation for rules, guidelines, requirements, and restrictions. Sometimes they are grouped into sections, but frequently they are scattered throughout the solicitation. Also check any general guidelines or terms and conditions the sponsor may have - there may be additional restrictions or requirements found there that also apply to the program or competition you're applying to.

3. Does the project speak to funder priorities?

The next step: check to see that the project fits the funder's or the program's priorities. This is particularly important if you haven't interacted with the program or the funder recently. Funders routinely change their interests. This can be as simple as tweaking a solicitation to reflect a new emphasis that's still in the same general area - or it can mean a complete overhaul of the funder's programs and priorities. It's just as important to ensure that the funding opportunity aligns with your organization's vision, mission, and goals.

Basically, the core research topics supported by the major federal funding agencies include:

Agency	Research Supported
Commerce (includes NOAA, NIST)	Weather forecasting and climate monitoring, fisheries management, science of weights and measures, broadband technology, economic development
Defense (includes DOD, NSA, CDMRP)	Development of military technology, training and protection of military personnel (including veterans), information security, encryption
Energy (includes DOE)	Energy policy, energy production, nuclear energy, nuclear safety, energy-related research
Education (includes Dept of Ed)	Support state and local efforts to improve student achievement, educational equity, and access to educational opportunities for all students.
Interior (includes BLM, USGS, NPS)	Management and conservation of federal lands, natural resources, geological monitoring, and national monuments and historic sites
Justice	Technology for criminal justice application including law enforcement and corrections, forensics, and judicial processes, as well as criminology, criminal justice, and related social science research.
NASA	Earth and planetary science; astrophysics and space science; heliophysics and the sun; biological and physical sciences; lunar science; aeronautics; human space travel
Art (includes National Endowment for the Arts, NEA)	Supporting excellence in the arts, both new and established; bringing the arts to all Americans; and providing leadership in arts education.
Humanities (includes National Endowment for the Humanities, NEH)	Museums, historic sites, colleges, universities, K-12 teachers, libraries, public television and radio stations, research institutions, independent scholars, and nonprofits doing research in the humanities and humanistic social sciences as defined in Section 3(a) of the National Foundation on the Arts and Humanities Act of 1965 .
NIH	Biomedical and public health research
NSF	Fundamental research and education in all non-medical fields of science and engineering
Agriculture (includes USDA)	Global food supply and security; climate and energy needs; nutrition and childhood obesity; food safety; education and science literacy; rural-urban interdependence/rural prosperity

The broader the scope covered by a solicitation or a program is, the more important it is to understand whether the funder will accept proposals on any topic that falls within the broad area of interest. Sometimes a funder may want to prioritize one or more lines of research - either for the foreseeable future or on some kind of rotating schedule. This information may not be easy to determine just from looking at the published guidelines or the interest statements on the funder's website. Your RD professional may be able to offer broader insight based on results from previous proposals to the same program - but you may also need to contact program staff about it. See the "[Reaching Out: Best Practices for Contacting Program Officers](#)" resource in the EMERGE Resource Library for additional information on how best to do so.

RD SAYS:

Foundations tend to change their funding priorities more frequently (and more radically) than do governmental agencies and other funders. Foundations typically change priorities every five to seven years, and may completely stop funding programs they've been investing in for years.

4. Is the proposal likely to be competitive?

After looking at the eligibility criteria - which is the threshold for applying for funding - now it's time to start thinking about both the suitability of the program (and the funding level) for your work, and also whether or not you and your team are competitive for a particular program.

Eligibility will get you into the room, but it's competitiveness that gets you funded.

5. Will the program provide enough funding to cover project costs?

When looking at potential funding opportunities, have at least a rough sense of how much funding you'll need to complete your project. Your research development or research administration team can help you draw up a rough budget, but make sure you ask for everything you need to do the work. That list includes, but is certainly not limited to, costs for personnel (you, your collaborators at your institution, any students - graduate or undergraduate - or postdocs, technical staff), fringe benefits, equipment, project travel, materials and supplies, data management and sharing costs, consultant fees, publication costs, incentives for human subjects, animal care costs, tuition remission, and applicable indirect costs. There may also be things the solicitation requires you to include in the budget (like an annual meeting for PIs of funded projects, or the costs for managing and storing data - even after the project ends - that you will generate).

It's quite common in some disciplines (especially, though not only, the arts and the humanities) to seek multiple grants for different parts of the same project. Doing that is always an option if no funder or program will provide all of the funding needed to do the work - but it does make more work for the investigator, and increases the chances that the project may not get finished on time - so if there is a program that will fund the entire project in one go, that's a program to put at the top of your list.

Should you need to approach multiple funders or multiple programs to cover the full costs of the project, prioritize funders and/or programs

that will give you enough money to keep the number of grants needed to the bare minimum. You will also want to alert each funder that you are seeking funding for the same project from a different source. Describe how each piece fits together until the whole project is done. A good strategy for doing that is to break the project into discrete parts, with minimal overlap between them. That makes it easier to convince the funders that you aren't trying to get funded twice to do the same work. Where that isn't possible, be explicit about how much overlap there is between relevant parts of the full project, and indicate your willingness to work with the funders to minimize any unallowable overlap between projects if most or all of them are funded.

6. Are there restrictions you can't work with?

Next, check whether the sponsor restricts how funding can be used - and if so, whether or not accepting those restrictions will affect your ability to complete the proposed project. For example, if you plan to have a graduate student do some of the research work for the project, but the program you're considering won't pay graduate student stipends (or sometimes it's tuition that isn't allowable), you might want to consider approaching a different program that doesn't have that restriction.

Note that some funding opportunities may have restrictions that could prevent you from seeking additional funding (such as limiting the number of proposals you can submit as PI or co-PI, or on the number of awards you can have from the program at one time). You want to be sure these restrictions are properly addressed and that they do not apply when you are seeking additional funding.

Another restriction to consider is whether the sponsor requires some level of matching funds or cost-sharing. Cost sharing, cost matching, or matching funds all refer to the same thing: a situation in which the applicant contributes resources to a project above and beyond the funds received from the funder. This can be mandatory (required by the funder) or voluntary, and can involve cash in hand, materials and supplies, time for volunteers or staff members, etc.

Universities commonly resist offering cost-sharing or matching funds except when the funder explicitly requires them as part of being eligible for funding from that program, or because there is a law or policy that requires it. As university budgets shrink, it is likely to become even harder to find hard dollars for cost-sharing - but there may be other ways of meeting a mandatory cost-sharing requirement. Here, too, ask your RD professional or your research administrator about what the funder allows, what your institution's policies are, and whether you can meet a cost-sharing requirement in ways that don't require cash contributions.

Sometimes, restrictions go beyond funding. For example, are there questions or activities the funder won't support? (Gun violence is a

If a funder doesn't allow you to spend money on something you need to complete the project, and if there isn't another sponsor you can approach that will pay for it, you may be able to support that part of the project from institutional funds, or returned indirect costs. Ask your RD professional or your research administrator about options.

common prohibited subject, as are political activities.) If doing the work you want to do involves such a question or an activity, then you will want to find a different funder to pay for it. Similarly, if your project involves working with members of a particular group that the funder either doesn't allow to participate in projects that it funds or restricts the kinds of activities you can involve them with, you may want to find a different competition for your proposal. An alternative in a situation like that would be to tailor your research, scholarship, or creative activity to what you can get funding to do. Be mindful that such a decision does not respect your academic freedom to research what interests you, and may also negatively impact your research career.

Certain funders (most commonly corporate or industry partners, but also some federal sponsors/programs) may want to review - or approve - any publications or presentations that arise from work you do with their money. It is very important to understand the difference between reviewing and approving, and equally important to know which one the sponsor intends. Publication of research findings is the lifeblood of a university. Faculty depend on publications to make a case for merit pay, for tenure, and for promotion. Students must be able to publish their original research if they are to be able to complete their graduate programs (or senior theses/capstone projects at the undergraduate level).

If the funder just wants the opportunity to review a manuscript or a presentation to make sure it doesn't contain any proprietary or confidential information that might compromise their ability to operate their business, secure copyright or patent rights on an invention or other form of intellectual property (IP), and if they don't insist on too long a delay between review and release of the manuscript for submission, universities will accept the restriction. But if what the funder wants is the ability to forbid publication or dissemination of the information, or the right to make changes that might compromise the integrity of the research or otherwise restrict the freedom to pursue research wherever it may lead, that is typically not acceptable.

Similarly, if the funder wants to own all the IP resulting from the proposed research (or, as with the Petroleum Research Fund of the American Chemical Society, requires the investigator to dedicate it to the public good), the university's willingness to accept the restriction will depend on a number of factors. First and foremost of those is whether the university (as many do) claims an ownership interest in the intellectual property developed by its faculty and students. If so, then the university is unlikely to want to give away that IP. If the investigator owns the IP, then as long as they understand the implications of the decision to accept the funding and don't care about retaining rights to any IP that may develop from it, then the university may not mind accepting the restriction.

7. Types of Funding and Their Implications

Different types of funding have different implications for what's required of the investigator and how much the funder is going to be involved in conducting the project. You need to understand which type of funding you (typically your university) would receive if your proposal is funded, and if you're willing to accept the implications that come along with that type of funding. If not, then you'll want to pursue a different opportunity.

There are four basic types of funding: gifts, grants, cooperative agreements, and contracts. In very broad, simplistic terms, they can be defined as follows:

- **Gift** - Money that is freely given to support an individual, an organization, a program, or an activity. There is no specific objective in mind, no defined scope of work to be completed, and no transfer of anything of value is made to the funder. Usually the funder asks for some kind of acknowledgement of its support, but even that is not always the case. Gifts generally have the fewest restrictions on how funds can be used.
- **Grant** - The funder reviews and approves a set of objectives or a defined scope of work. Usually - but not always - a detailed budget is required. Unspent funds may have to be returned to the funder at the end of the project. There is a defined period of performance, when work is completed. Frequently, reports (technical, financial, or both) are required. The investigator is expected to use their best efforts to complete the approved scope of work within the time allowed.
- **Cooperative Agreement** - Very similar to a grant, but the funder will be more directly involved in the design and conduct of the project.
- **Contract** - Contracts are more common for the support of applied research (such as making improvements in the performance of a device or a process), but they can also support basic research. The main difference between a contract and a grant is that the investigator agrees to provide specific deliverables at stated times - and accepts a legal obligation to do so. If that obligation is not met, the investigator can be penalized (including legal action), required to give up the remainder of the funding, or to complete the contract as it was signed even without additional funding. Contracts often have more restrictions on the use of funds than either grants or cooperative agreements.

Contracts can also have different forms. The two most common types of contracts supporting research are fixed-price and cost-reimbursable contracts. A fixed-price contract means pretty much what it says: the investigator and the funder agree to complete the scope of work for a fixed amount of money. From a financial standpoint a cost-reimbursable contract works a lot like a grant: the investigator conducts the work, and

Surprisingly, determining whether something is a gift, a grant, cooperative agreement, or a contract is a very complex process subject to quite a lot of interpretation. Always check with your RD professional or your research administrator before proceeding.

submits invoices to the funder at stated intervals which the funder then approves to reimburse the institution for the work already completed on the project. There may be further restrictions on how much money is available to the project at stated times, or reimbursement may be tied to production of deliverables or completion of agreed project milestones.

8. Is there enough time?

Timing is important for a number of reasons, not least of which is the amount of time and effort required to develop and submit a competitive, compelling proposal. So your first question is how much time do you have before the next submission deadline - and can you do everything listed in the scope of work in the time available? If not, consider putting that particular competition on the pile to come back to another time, or, if it's a recurring opportunity, defer submission of your proposal to the next proposal cycle.

Sometimes, though, you don't get that opportunity. A collaborator or a colleague reaches out to you in a panic because another member of their team has dropped out at the last minute. Even though there are only a few days or a week to go before the deadline, they ask if you'd be willing to join their project. Carefully consider whether or not you actually can do everything that needs to be done to support such a project in the time you have - and also ask your research office if they can do the work they need to do within the same timeframe. If the answer to either or both of these questions is no, then you should tell your collaborator or colleague that you're grateful for the chance to participate, but you just can't take on the extra work at the present time.

Timing is important in other ways, too. If you need to gain access to a field site (to conduct an archaeological dig, or to collect plant or mineral samples), or if you're planning to recruit participants from a community or a group that you aren't already working with - you'll need to build in time to secure that access, recruit those participants, or get buy-in from your project partners.

That buy-in is crucial when working with various populations. You must first gain their trust before they even agree to participate in the project: and that process can take months or years. Let's say you want to work with materials science and engineering, you will need to explain the project to the community and possibly one or more relevant governing bodies (advisory boards, industry leaders), then secure explicit consent from each of them to the design and conduct of the project. Funders are increasingly requiring that you document such consent for proposals that involve work with various communities, so if you don't already have

Working with your research office is important at every step, and every phase, of this journey. We cannot stress this point enough. A good way to help you decide whether or not to join any project - but especially one that comes to you at the last minute - is to ask yourself what you can and will give up or put down if you accept this invitation.

it, you will need to adjust your submission timeline accordingly.

Lastly, consider the funder's timeline for the review and award processes. If you submit your proposal to the next deadline, and the funder completes its review and award process on time, will you be able to start the project when you need to? Will you have funds in hand (or at least the ability to spend grant funding) when you need to buy an important piece of equipment or make travel arrangements to take advantage of a window of opportunity to do work in a specific place? If not, again, you'll need to adjust your submission timeline (or your project timeline) accordingly.

9. What's the history?

Understanding the history of interactions with a particular funder (or funder's program) is another key contributor to funding success - and one that is often overlooked. This can happen because an investigator doesn't know whom to ask, or because they don't see the full picture because they only know about projects they've personally been involved with..

This is something that your RD or research administration professional can help with. If you have limited or no experience with a funder or a particular opportunity, ask whether your institution has a history with that funder or with that program. If you have partners on the project at other institutions, ask them to do the same.

If you do have a history of working with them, that history is ideally a positive one. If it isn't, or if you don't have any history of working with them, you have a couple of options. First, consider approaching a different program or funder to support this project. Otherwise, you will need to do some extra work in your proposal to convince the funder to support you. (Doing that extra work can also be a factor in how much time you need before submitting the proposal, as we just discussed in the previous section.)

Many solicitations express a wish to encourage new investigators to apply, ask for proposals representing innovative, cutting-edge projects, or both. But when we look at what actually gets funded, funders seem to prefer funding the "tried and true" projects. It's easier to understand this attitude when you realize that programs are giving away thousands or millions of dollars of other people's money - and that those people naturally expect to see some form of return on their investment. Spending too much money on risky projects that don't work out may mean that the people who provide the money to give out to others may stop giving it to you, or reduce the amount they're willing to give.

Sometimes, funders allow you to spend money before the award period has technically started. But this is not universally allowed, and there may be other policies, procedures, etc., to be followed. Check with your research administrator to see whether you can spend money before the award begins and, if so, what you need to do for that to happen.

So if you (or anyone else on your project team) don't have some **history** with a funder or program - or if the history you do have is a few years in the past - you'll need to take extra care in the proposal to show how you're going to mitigate that risk. The same is true if you and your collaborators have only just started working together, or if you and the project team don't already have a good working relationship with other institutions, populations, communities, etc., that you will need to access. Your research development professional can help you address the need to reduce the specific risks you're facing.

10. Vibe Check

Lastly, is there anything about this sponsor that makes you (or anyone else on your team) uncomfortable? Anything that might create friction or lead to issues with the intended research populations? Or anything that would constitute a conflict of interest (or even the appearance of such a conflict)? For example, it's probably not a good idea to take funding from a company that operates contrary to your values. If something just doesn't sit right, move on and find another way to support your project.

Read the Guidelines

"Read the guidelines" seems like such an obvious point that we wouldn't need to mention it. Sadly, experience over many years and multiple institutions has shown us that it still needs to be said - and repeatedly. Also, as we noted above, the "guidelines" to read mean more than just the solicitation for the program you're considering applying to. Also check the funder's standard guidelines for proposal writing, and any terms and conditions that will apply to an award you receive from the program, and all applicable FAQs - all of those contain information that's critical for you to know, understand, and follow.

Once you've narrowed your list of potential funding opportunities to a reasonable size, your next move is to carefully read the guidelines for each one. Pay particular attention whenever you see any of these **four** words (or expressions that include them):

- Must
- Should
- Expect
- Require

If you spot such a condition, and it requires you to do something you cannot or don't want to do, or if it prohibits you from doing something you need or want to do or that would interfere with your ability to complete the project, then don't apply for that particular opportunity. Move to the next one in the stack.

There may be times when, no matter how carefully you crafted your

Some of the things you could do to address the lack of history include taking extra care to explain your choices for methods, analyses, and timing; developing a detailed plan for project management; discussing potential pitfalls or roadblocks you might encounter while doing the project work and ways you can work around them; or include an appropriate collaborator with more experience with or access to an institution, population, or resource that you need; and being very clear in your expected impact.

If you see any of those four words, it's a strong sign from the funder that they consider whatever they refer to as important - something you need to do, something to include in your proposal, or something you can't do, can't request, or can't include in your proposal. Not understanding or not complying with such conditions may mean your proposal is returned without review, or that it reviews badly. Some years ago, the Harry Frank Guggenheim Foundation included these lines in its proposal guidelines: "And if you submit a budget that contradicts any of these carefully described guidelines, we will have reason to think of you as a careless reader and thoughtless applicant. This will inevitably be reflected in our estimation of the potential of your scholarship."

search or how diligently you weeded out opportunities that weren't a good fit for you or for your project, you're still left with multiple options - or with questions about either eligibility or fit with the program's priorities - that you just can't answer on your own. When you get to that point, it's time to check with your RD professional and then call a program officer. See: Wright, G., and Spires, M. (2025). [Reaching Out: Best Practices for Contacting Program Officers](#). The NORDP Consultants Program.

RESOURCES

- A. Stone, David A. "How Your Grant Proposal Compares." The Chronicle of Higher Education, 29 July 2009, <https://www.chronicle.com/article/how-your-grant-proposal-compares/>. Accessed 7 November 2024.

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